

One-pot synthesis of novel heterocyclic compounds via tandem reactions

C. A. M. A. Huq* and S. Sivakumar

Post Graduate and Research Department of Chemistry, The New College, Affiliated to the University of Madras, Chennai-600 014, India

E-mail : drmdabdulhuq@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Novel heterocyclic compounds (**2**), (**4**) and (**6**) have been prepared by a tandem oxy-Cope rearrangement/S_N displacement reaction, a tandem dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement/nucleophilic substitution at carbonyl carbon and a tandem anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement/transannular reaction respectively. The oxy-Cope rearrangement involves the π bonds of the pyridyl rings which forms the 1,5-hexadiene system necessary for a [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement.

Keywords : Tandem reaction, 2-pyridyl magnesium bromide, transannular reaction, oxy-Cope rearrangement.

Introduction

The oxy-Cope process is tolerant to various functional groups. Hence it is often convenient to incorporate within the starting alcohol, features that are conducive to subsequent tandem reaction like transannular reaction, cycloaddition, ene reaction and nucleophilic displacement. There is a report¹ of this route being employed for the synthesis of polycyclic structures. Tandem aromatic oxy-Cope rearrangement/transannular reaction involving aromatic rings such as 1- and 2-naphthyl, 2-furanyl and 2-benzofuranyl as one of the substituent have also been reported². There is also a report³ on tandem [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement/thermally induced [2+2]-cycloaddition approach to a synthesis of carboxylic spiro oxy indoles.

Previously we have reported⁴ the first instance of diaromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement involving π bonds of both naphthyl rings of 1,2-dinaphthyl diols derived from cyclic α diketones. We have also reported⁵ the synthesis of functionalized polycyclic compounds via novel aromatic oxy-Cope rearrangement wherein the two π bonds of the two phenyl rings are involved in the [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement. Recently we have reported⁶ a one-pot synthesis of 3,3-diaryl oxindoles by the addition of various Grignard reagents to *N*-substituted isatins. In continuation of this work, we herein report a first instance of a tandem reaction, involving dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement for the synthesis of novel heterocyclic

compounds containing pyridyl rings. Here the two π bonds of two pyridyl rings form the 1,5-hexadiene system necessary for [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement.

Results and discussion

In an attempt to prepare 9,10-dipyridylphenanthrene 9,10-diol (**1**), by the addition of 4 equivalents of 2-pyridylmagnesium bromide to 9,10-phenanthraquinone, we could not isolate the diol, but instead we could isolate 10-(pyridine-2-yloxy)phenanthren-9-ol (**2**) (Scheme 1a) as a pale yellow solid. The IR spectrum of **2** showed a broad peak at 3435 cm⁻¹ due to enolic OH. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **2** showed signals for aromatic protons in the region δ 7.10 to 8.70 and the enolic OH gave a singlet at δ 8.89. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of **2** showed a signal for $>C=C-OH$ at δ 147.3 and signals for $>C-O-C<$ carbons at δ 141.6 and 163.9 respectively. The mass spectrum showed (M⁺+1) peak at 288.1432. Finally the structure was further confirmed by single crystal X-ray analysis⁷ of **2**. The formation of **2** involves a tandem oxy-Cope rearrangement/S_N displacement reaction of the intermediate diol (**1**) (Scheme 2). A similar mechanism is reported⁸.

In continuation of the above work we attempted to prepare 1,2-dipyridylacenaphthene-1,2-diol (**3**) by the addition of 4 equivalents of 2-pyridylmagnesium bromide to 1,2-acenaphthaquinone in dry THF. But instead of the

diol (**3**), we could only isolate (**4**) (Scheme 1b) as a pale brown solid. The IR spectrum of **4** showed a broad peak at 3434 cm^{-1} due to OH of $-\text{COOH}$, a peak at 1769 cm^{-1} due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of COOH and a peak at 1719 cm^{-1} due to aryl carbonyl. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **4** showed signals for aromatic protons in the region δ 7.84 to 8.67. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **4** showed a signal at δ 160.5 due to carbon of carbonyl group of carboxylic acid and a signal at δ 188.1 due to carbon of the aryl carbonyl. The mass spectrum showed (M^+) peak at 354.4703. The formation of **4** involves a tandem dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement/nucleophilic substitution at carbonyl carbon (tetrahedral mechanism), followed by air oxidation (Scheme 3). A similar air oxidation is reported⁹.

Similarly the addition of 4 equivalents of 2-pyridylmagnesium bromide to benzil in dry THF, we could only isolate (9*a*,10-dihydro-10-hydroxy-10-phenylpyrido-[2,3-*b*]indolizin-9*a*-yl)(phenyl)methanone (**6**) (Scheme 1c), as a white solid instead of the diol **5**. The IR spectrum of **6** showed a peak at 3415 cm^{-1} due to OH and a peak at 1678 cm^{-1} due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of aryl carbonyl. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **6** showed D_2O exchangeable signal at δ 1.68

Scheme 3. The mechanism of formation of **4**.

due to OH proton, signals at δ 4.59 and 5.97 due to olefinic protons of the dihydropyridine ring and signals in the region δ 7.26 to 7.94 due to aromatic protons. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **6** showed a signal at δ 147.6 due to -C-OH carbon and a signal at δ 198.7 due to carbon of the aryl carbonyl. The mass spectrum showed ($M^+ + 2$) peak at 368.0847. The formation of **6** involves a tandem dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement/transannular ring closure followed by air oxidation (Scheme 4).

In conclusion our work is a first instance where tandem reactions are used for a one-pot synthesis of novel heterocyclic compounds from simple starting materials.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) on silica gel. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in deuterio chloroform (CDCl_3) using tetra methyl silane (TMS) as an internal standard on a BRUKER 300 spectrometer at 400 mega Hertz (MHz). ^{13}C NMR were re-

corded on a BRUKER 300 spectrometer at 100 MHz and mass spectra on JEOL DX-303 spectrometer. Tetrahydrofuran was freshly distilled from sodium benzophenone ketyl before use. The reactions were carried out in a Schlenk type glass apparatus under nitrogen atmosphere.

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds (2), (4) and (6) :

To a solution of 2-pyridylmagnesium bromide in dry THF at 0 °C under N_2 atmosphere [prepared from magnesium (Mg) (0.03 mol) and 2-bromopyridine (0.03 mol)], the dione (0.01 mol) in dry THF was added dropwise over a period of 15–20 min. After completion of addition, the mixture was stirred at 0 °C under N_2 atmosphere for 2 h followed by stirring at room temperature under N_2 atmosphere for 3 h. After the completion of reaction as evidenced by TLC, the reaction was quenched with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl) (50 mL). The product was extracted with diethyl ether (2×50 ml). The ether layer was washed with water fol-

Scheme 4. Mechanism of formation of 6.

lowed by brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. Purification of the crude product by column chromatography on silica gel (100–200 mesh) using hexane-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent gave the corresponding product.

Experimental data for (2) : A pale yellow solid. Yield 75%, m.p. 145 °C (Found : C, 79.40; H, 4.51; N, 4.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$: C, 79.44; H, 4.56; N, 4.80%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3435 (O-H str.), 3074 (C-H str.), 2306 (enolic), 1603 (C=C str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) δ (ppm) : 7.10 (1H, t, J 7 Hz), 7.20 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz), 7.47–7.60 (1H, m), 7.67–7.84 (1H, m, due to protons of the pyridyl ring), 8.03 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 8.18–8.26 (2H, m), 8.47–8.53 (2H, m), 8.63–8.73 (2H, m), due to protons of the benzene ring, 8.89 (1H, s, enolic OH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 111.9, 119.3, 121.1 (2C), 122.5, 122.8, 123.3, 124.6, 127.0 (4C), 128.3, 129.6, 130.6, 140.6, 141.6, 147.3, 163.9;

Mass spectrum m/z : 288.1432 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

Experimental data for (4) : A pale brown solid. Yield 80%, m.p. 155 °C (Found : C, 74.3; H, 3.90; N, 7.87. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 74.5; H, 3.95; N, 7.90%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3434 (br, O-H str. of COOH), 1769 (C=O str. of COOH), 1719 (C=O str.), 1581 (C=C str.); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3/TMS) δ (ppm) : 7.84–7.90 (4H, m, protons of the monosubstituted pyridyl ring), 8.14–8.15 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, protons of the disubstituted pyridyl ring), 8.30–8.36 (4H, m, protons of the naphthalene ring), 8.65–8.67 (2H, m, peri protons of the naphthalene ring); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 118.9, 122.1, 123.4, 124.1, 124.9, 126.5, 127.5, 128.5, 128.6, 130.3, 131.1, 131.8, 132.6, 133.5, 133.7, 134.4, 135.3, 136.2, 137.6, 145.4, 160.6, 188.1; Mass spectrum m/z : 354.4703 (M^+).

Experimental data for (6) : A white solid. Yield 80%, m.p. 110 °C (Found : C, 78.65; H, 4.90; N, 7.63. Calcd.

for C₂₄H₁₈N₂O₂ : C, 78.68; H, 4.92; N, 7.65%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3415 (-OH str.), 1678 (C=O str.), 1595 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) δ (ppm) : 1.68 (1H, br, s, D₂O exchangeable OH proton), 4.59 (2H, s), 5.97 (2H, s), olefinic protons of the dihydropyridine ring, 7.26–7.42 (5H, m, protons of the benzene ring), 7.51–7.55 (5H, m, protons of the benzene ring), 7.92–7.94 (3H, m, protons of the pyridine ring); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) δ (ppm) : 76.2, 76.8, 77.3, 88.3, 90.5, 109.5, 121.0, 122.1, 123.7, 127.8 (2C), 128.6 (2C), 129.1 (2C), 133.5, 133.9, 136.8 (2C), 139.0, 143.5, 147.6, 151.5, 198.7; Mass spectrum *m/z* : 368.0847 (M⁺+2).

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